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CLOGGING MECHANISMS AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES IN ARTIFICIAL RECHARGE SYSTEMS

*Abror Gadaev*¹

Samarkand State Architectural and Construction university, Faculty of construction, Department Environmental engineering, Samarkand, Uzbekistan
1ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-7343-8534>

*Sevara Usanova*²

Samarkand State Architectural and Construction university, Faculty of construction, Department Environmental engineering, Samarkand, Uzbekistan
<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-8327-3834>

Mammadov Nurmammad, Azerbaijan Architecture and Construction University, Baku, Azerbaijan.
ORCID ID:0000-0002-0508-0439

Abstract:

Groundwater is mainly used for water supply in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In artesian wells, due to a decrease in filtration, it leads to a decrease in discharge. In this article, the dissolution kinetics of saline sediments is studied.

Annotation

The water resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan are limited; the dry and hot climate requires the use of mainly groundwater for the water supply system.

These are multi-thousand wells and their operation. The flow rate of water intake wells decreases significantly over time due to the combined impact of mechanical, chemical and biological colmatage processes, which results in the deposition of sediments in the porous medium of gravel packing and on filters. The withdrawal of water from the well changes the hydrodynamics of the formation, resulting in an abrupt shift in the chemical equilibrium in the groundwater near the well. Salt deposition means a decrease in the porosity of the rock and the filter, which leads to a decrease in the filtration of rocks in the near-filter zone and the filter. Reducing filtration in artesian wells leads to a decrease in flow rate. This article is devoted to the study of the kinetics of deposition and the evolution of colmatation of wells. The research results serve to establish the correct parameters for the method of removing salt deposits from wells.

Keywords: *Artificial recharge; Clogging mechanisms; Groundwater; Prevention; Redevelopment*

Introduction

The penetrated and retained water occupying all the voids of associated geological strata under the earth's surface is termed as underground water, or otherwise, groundwater (GW). Approximately 97% of the world water in the oceans is salty water and two-thirds of remaining fresh water in confined (mountainous and arctic) regions is entrapped as ice. 98% of the liquid water is groundwater, whereas streams, rivers, and lakes hold only about 2%. Groundwater exists in soils and rocks. Generally, in

the aeration zone or unsaturated zone, both water and air filled the gaps between the soils, while underlying this layer is the saturated zone where only water fills the void spaces, i.e. aquifer, and water in the aquifer is termed as groundwater. Groundwater as a renewable and important natural resource serves many purposes, such as domestic water supply, for the public and private sectors; irrespective of intensive research on water reuse, desalination processes as well as advanced treatment techniques; agriculture use which mainly includes irrigation, animal watering and agricultural productions; and industrial and construction uses. In addition, groundwater has been increasingly used in the areas of energy such as aquifer thermal energy storage (ATES) projects. In artificial recharge-discharge systems, groundwater has recently been extracted for controlling temperatures of different engineering structures by using heat pumps due to its sufficient availability and unique property of relative constant temperature throughout the year. This eco-friendly technology allows the groundwater with heat energy to be abstracted and then injected into the aquifer through an injection well during the winter. Similarly, in summer, the water is usually pumped to reduce the temperature of different engineering structures. By pumping water into the wells, the groundwater recharge can be artificially carried out by applying the induced artificial recharge process. Although similar in design, the major difference between the artificial recharge and water supply wells is that the surrounding aquifer recharged with water flowing from the recharge well is driven by either injection pump induced head or a gravity head. In an injection well system, a substantial amount of water is being pushed through a small aquifer volume.

In an artificial recharge system (ARS), however, clogging is the major problem for the recharge system to work smoothly and is often influenced by different interdependent physic-bio-chemical factors that may have different behaviors in porous and fractured media. Clogging can also reduce the flow to the aquifer due to the blockage of some available pores, which ultimately reduces the permeability of the porous medium. In many cases, injected water with low quality can cause the clogging in deep wells. These injected effluents usually undergo secondary biological processes such as the combination of extended aeration and/or aerobic digestion; among them, high concentration of suspended solids (SS), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), N-compounds, and grease and oil often may remain in these effluents for quite a long time. In addition, during water injection some other factors such as SS, total dissolved solids (TDS), sodium adsorption ratio and certain nutrient concentrations are also of great concern. These factors might stimulate microbial activity and can cause clogging in the surroundings of injection well, the influence of which can span further into the aquifer system. According to, 80% of the aquifer storage and recovery sites faced clogging problems, approximately half of which were caused by physical clogging due to the SS infiltration, while 15% were caused by biological growth and microbial activity and 10% were attributed to chemical precipitation. There were also other clogging processes, i.e. 10%-air entrapment, 5%-clay swelling and dispersion, and 5%- mechanical jamming and mobilization of aquifer sediments. Therefore, by considering these cases, it is necessary to pay attention to conceptual issues of the well clogging problem in order to develop eco- friendly and economy-wise strategies for combating this nuisance global problem. The present paper attempts to review the basic mechanisms, types, and characteristics of the recharge well clogging together with the potential methods, measures & redevelopments for clogging prevention and remediation in artificial recharge systems.

Groundwater recharge

Replenishment of an aquifer with water is defined as a recharge process (RP). This is termed as natural process when precipitated water percolates or filtrates via soil pores or rock fractures into an aquifer. Natural recharge process of groundwater (GW) strongly depends on local climate and the properties of vadose zone and aquifer. Contrarily, in artificial recharge (AR) system, water is introduced on or into the ground where the applied surface water is infiltrated and moved down to

aquifers to enhance GW pools or resources. Briefly, an AR process involves the transmission of water present at surface towards the subsurface aquifers via anthropogenic interventions. reported that this water transmission is done by water accumulating the water on the surface of soils or rocks with special structures such as furrows, basins, ditches and others or by introducing it to the infiltrating trenches, shafts, or vadose zone wells, or directly injecting it into the aquifer via recharge wells. Generally, there are three ways of AR, i.e. (I) surface infiltration basin (mostly installed in soil layers preferentially with sandy soil and limited clay), (II) recharge wells sunk in vadose zone where surface infiltration is difficult due to hydraulic properties and economic factor, and (III) injection well with direct recharge to confined aquifers. In most cases, the AR is achieved by pumping and injecting water into the wells or by deploying water on upper layers, following by its seepage into the aquifer involved through the unsaturated or vadose zones. The augmentation of GW reservoirs by AR can be considered as a supplemental activity to the natural recharge process. It is hence a useful approach to enhancing the groundwater availability and improving water quality of the aquifer. However, the most critical issue that challenges the efficiency of different recharge systems is clogging. Therefore, understanding the types and mechanisms of clogging in artificial recharge systems and their possible control measures will provide the conceptual framework to mitigate the clogging problem

Methods for potential clogging rate

Potential clogging rate for an artificial recharge system can be predicted by using different methods which include modified fouling index (MFI), parallel filter index (PFI), organic carbon (OC) content i.e. assimilable organic carbon (AOC) and biodegradable organic carbon (b DOC) contents of the recharging water, as well as mathematical, empirical and analytical models; MFI describes SS contents of the water. The AOC is a microbial determination protocol that relies on plating and incubation technique of water sample for Pseudomonas fluorescence type bacterial growth followed by counting number of bacterial colonies. The results in protocol are expressed on the basis of acetate solution’s carbon concentration yielding the similar microbial growth.

As the AOC is usually less than 1% of dissolved OC (DOC), the b DOC may be a better parameter for the estimation of biological clogging compared to the AOC, especially when the OC concentration is high. In addition, it is more feasible to determine the b DOC content than that of the AOC, because

Fig. 1 Conceptual framework of the types of clogging that can occur during the recharge process

DOC test relies on the degradability of OC in different soil tests i.e. columns or soil slurry batch tests. The estimation of PFI relies on the flow of recharging water through appropriately packed columns with suitable aquifer materials. Thus, an advanced alarming factor can be established due to the faster clogging rate in columns compared to field tests. The MFI indicates the inversely filtered flow slope versus filtered volume on a cumulative basis, which is the best parameter to predict clogging potential of the water that penetrates into the aquifer. Comparatively, the other clogging parameters such as SS content, b DOC and flow tested in packed columns might have some limitations as the indicators of relative clogging potentials. However, these parameters might not be suitable for actual clogging prediction because the injection rate might decline in a recharge operation. Therefore, more detailed study on full scale recharge well test is direly needed to formulate the criteria for a better design and management of recharge well. Furthermore, a timely recognition of clogging generally provides valuable information to restore the original capacity of the system by deploying an appropriate redevelopment approach. However, the predictability of well clogging remains question- able, in spite of many efforts have been made by using different parametric indices for both physical (e.g. total SS and turbidity) and biological (e.g. total OC, DOC and AOC) clogging. There is a general reduction in concentrations of BOD, SS, pathogens, and N along with the water infiltrates through vadose zone reported that there is generally no analytical or numerical/mathematical tool to study the deposition and clogging of the porous media. Using modeling approach to predicting well clogging problem has been a challenge due to the interdependence and diverse natures of soil clogging mechanisms. Mathematical models used for predicting the movement of suspended particles (SP) in the aquifer are unable to verify the experimental data due to the variability of associated parameters and soil and environmental conditions.

Types and mechanisms of clogging

Different types, causes, and mechanisms of clogging based on the cases reported in the pertinent literature are summarized in Table 1. It is hard to distinguish the clogging mechanisms due to the interdependence of cases studied and complexity of well clogging. For example, reactive models can simulate different scenarios of temperature perturbation, which is in relation to potential clogging risk, i.e. the precipitation of carbonate, calcium sulfate and clay minerals taking place in the “hot bubble” and the precipitation of barium sulfate and clay minerals in the “cold bubble”. Well clogging caused by SS can be recognized as a practical implication of microbe mediated reactions in soil. Similarly, it is hard to distinguish the processes of bioclogging and chemical clogging because some reactions in chemical clogging are mostly the microbial mediated ones. Hence, the uncoupling of clogging process is a challenge in practical situations.

Generally, clogging can be categorized as (I) mechanical/physical clogging due to suspended particulate matter in the water, (II) chemical clogging due to chemical reaction and substance precipitation in the aquifer, and (III) biological clogging due to the accumulation of microbial/ algal slimes and resultant redox products. Intrinsically, clogging is a physical phenomenon. In the meantime, it is also an interdependent and complex result of various physical, biological, and chemical processes, each of which is the combination of numerous processes impacted by different factors. For example, physical clogging may arise due to the presence of SS in recharging water, clay swelling and dispersion and mechanical jamming, etc.; the latter two that affect different types of clogging are separately categorized in few studies. Similarly, bio clogging may be due to microbial cells, extracellular polymers, gaseous byproducts, or microbe mediated insoluble precipitates. The chemical clogging phenomenon is extremely intricate because of different influencing factors that are acting as developmental agents in the chemical clogging. These influencing factors include the chemical components of the recharging water and groundwater in the aquifer, mineral composition of the aquifer media and environmental factors such as temperature, pressure, etc. In chemical clogging, chemical precipitation, and behavior of certain metal ions such as iron (Fe) and manganese (Mn) are

extremely important.

Table 1 Major clogging types and various influencing factors/causes and processes

Clogging types	Factors/causes	Processes
Physical	(I) The presence of suspended matter such as inorganic (clay, silt, etc.) and organic (organic matter, algae, sludge, etc.) in recharge water	(I) Filtration and deposition of suspended solids (SS) by the porous media, i.e. Filter function (diameter of SS > diameter of media pores) and deposition function (SS deposition on the pore wall due to gravity)
	(II) Presence of colloidal material and dispersal of clay particles due to ion exchange between recharging water and aquifers	* (II) Swelling of clays and dispersion
	(II) Mechanical compaction of aquifer materials due to high injection processes	* (III) Mechanical jamming and mobilization of aquifer sediments
Chemical	(I) Recharge water (aerobic), and native groundwater (anaerobic) containing soluble iron and manganese and aquifer material producing insoluble precipitates of iron and manganese oxides or hydroxides, e.g. formation of iron flakes from native ground water due to recharge of water with a pH and Eh in the range of ferric iron	(I) Blending and geochemical reactions between the recharge water and native groundwater resulting in the formation and chemical precipitations of insoluble precipitates of Fe and Mn (hydr) oxides
	(II) Mineral gradients of aquifers	(II) Mixing of cooler recharge water with native groundwater and the removal of dissolved air from the solution, i.e. the presence of air bubbles in the recharge water entering a well resulting in air entrapment or entrainment
	(III) Environmental factors such as temperature and pressure, etc.	* (III) Release of dissolved gases resulting in pore blocking air pockets in the aquifer, termed as air binding
	(IV) Entrained air in recharge water	(IV) Dissolution/precipitations of CaCO ₃ due to changes in pH and CO ₂
Biological	(I) The growth of bacteria (e.g. iron and manganese) and algae in the gravel pack and the surrounding formation	(I) Development of microbial growth and accumulation of cell bodies in the porous medium resulting in biofilms
	(II) The concentration of dissolved organic carbon (DOC), organic material, total nitrate, total phosphorus, and temperature etc.	(II) The production of bacterial extracellular polymers or polysaccharides forming soil-clogging biomass
	(III) Microbial mediated gas productions (nitrogen, methane, CO ₂)	(III) Microbial mediated accumulation of insoluble precipitates and redox products (IV) The entrapment of gaseous products resulting in soil pore blocking

*Clogging due to clay swelling and dispersion, mechanical jamming and air entrapment can be categorized into separate clogging categories.

Physical clogging

Clogging by suspended particles

Physical clogging occurs when small particles are deposited and detached during transport process. Suspended particles (SP) in the recharging water, soil size and porosity are the key factors for particle deposition. Physical clogging involves transport process, attaching process (deposition and retention) and de-attaching process (shearing and unclogging) of inert SP in the recharging water, resulting in the diminution of porosity of infiltrating space. At the same time, it gradually reduces the aquifer permeability and consequently the infiltration rate of recharge system, which has restricted the application of AR techniques in many areas. It was reported that approximately 70% of reduction in permeability of a recharge system was attributed to physical clogging).

Physical clogging can be classified into two types. The first type is the presence of SP in the injected water and the second one is the mobilization of finer soil particles in the aquifer triggered by the injection process (Fig. 2a-Fig. 2b). In terms of their particle composition, the SPs can be categorized into: (I) colloidal sized particles with particle size of less than 1 μm ; (II) intermediate particles (size: 1-30 μm); and (III) large sized particles (>30 μm). In an AR system, physical clogging may change over time due to the change in controlling forces such as those changed from volumetric to surface forces and vice-versa; and this behavior relies on flow velocity as well as the availability of reactive surfaces. Brownian diffusion also displays some significant function in characterizing the fate of colloidal fraction in the porous media. The formation of colloids can take place with the substance sourced from inorganic constituents, humus, and biological products. The GW usually has a low concentration of colloid; but this content can be changed due to chemical reactions in the water which induce the occurrence of colloid because of repulsive interactive forces occurring between colloidal fraction and grain formation. The variations in soil reaction (pH) and strength of ionic species are important factors in this context. Repulsive forces between particles can enhance and induce remobilization of colloidal fraction, when the injected water has less strength of ionic species than that of groundwater. Swelling and dispersion mechanisms of clay are related to this phenomenon. The pH augment enhances the dispersion of clay which ultimately leads to the reduction of the medium permeability. The unfavorable impact due to the quality of recharging water and aquifer media highlights the concern about clay swelling and dispersion. These fine-grained clay particles with negatively electronic charges are present in the form of threads, plates/flocks and they are normally bonded with the other positively charged particles. Although, some authors classified mechanical jamming (i.e. particle rearrangement) and clay expansion or dispersion into separate clogging categories, these clogging methods might be considered as specific categories of clogging caused by physical process as listed in Table 1. Filter function (where the SP particle size is larger than that of media pore space) and deposition function (in which the SP deposits on pore wall due to gravity) are the major reasons for physical clogging due to the SP. Different experimental results have shown that recharge water for aquifer storage and recovery (ASR) should have a safe limit of SS <2 ppm. Nevertheless, it is also reported that some aquifers with a high level of SS did not cause clogging because GW in the aquifer contains CaCO_3 .

In a surface-based system clogging, a proportional relationship exists between the clogging potential degree vs. surface clogging layer thickness and the SP concentration of recharged water. Generally, the focus for investigating physical clogging has mostly been placed on the surface of seepage zone, with limited ones on the inner part of the seeping zone. This is dependent on the seepage media properties, recharging water quality, particle size and its physicochemical characteristics, seepage capacity and recharge time duration. However, translocation of finer-grained materials, particularly clay colloids, is a recurring challenge for recharge systems to operate efficiently. Released clay colloids interact with surfaces, which will ultimately block the entire vadose and greatly reduce its permeability. Due to the infiltration and movement of water in vadose zone, separation of foreign and inert material takes place via different processes. The large particles with the size ranging from

1 μm to 10 μm either deposit as a surficial layer or are filtered by the topsoil, while the smaller SP ones ($<0.1 \mu\text{m}$) mobilize together with water via porous media and are influenced by physicochemical processes occurring in soil profile.

Fig. 2 (a) Physical clogging due to the suspended particles initially presented in the injected water; (b) Physical clogging due to the presence of fine soil particles from the aquifer; (c) Lay out of microbial biofilm that can cause bio-clogging; (d-f)

Deposited insoluble iron flakes produced upon the oxidation of soluble iron (Fe^{2+}) in a column experiment resulting in chemical clogging

Furthermore, soil compaction is another type of physical clogging, which mostly occurs on the surface of a recharge system due to excess water. Theoretically, there is a linear relationship between the water level of recharge basin and the recharge rate. However, because of unavoidable particle deposition and algal growth on the surface of the seeping zone, unreasonably increase in water level and decrease in recharge rate might occur simultaneously due to the compaction of clogging layers.

In a recharge basin system, finer-grained soils are more prone to clogging process than coarser-grained ones because small pores can easily be blocked by SS. Microbial growth on soil particles can result in significant reduction in effective porosity and, hence, affecting the infiltration capacity. In addition, downward migration, and near-surface accumulation of small-sized (clay sized or smaller) particles driven by the seepage force result in the formation of confining layer, which is known as micro-clogging. This phenomenon is a determining factor for the formation of crust in soil. In addition, dissolved impurities may convert to suspended ones during well injection due to physicochemical changes of the recharging water. For example, minute quantities of Fe and Mn in the water may fluctuate/ fall by flocculating or precipitating with CO_3 ; or influenced by the changes in pH and the clogging can occur again by those impurities present as SS.

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